

FLEXURAL BEHAVIOR OF CFRP REINFORCED BEAMS: A CASE STUDY WITH COMPARISONS TO STEEL REINFORCED ELEMENTS

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Abstract

The demand to develop high-performance building materials, energy-efficient designs and sustainable construction approaches has been rapidly growing in the recent years to overcome environmental challenges caused by the increasing CO₂ emissions. Carbon fiber-reinforced polymer (CFRP) is a high-performance material with appealing features that has the potential to replace steel reinforcement in wide range of structural applications. The investigation of the flexural behavior of carbon reinforced concrete elements is crucial for the design of these structures in practice and the calculation of deflections is needed to achieve admissible designs in the serviceability limit state (SLS). In this work, a recently developed generic model for the assessment of moment-curvature relation and load-deflection response of structural elements subjected to bending is used to investigate the flexural behavior of carbon reinforced beams using different cross-section configurations and material properties. Additionally, parallel studies with steel reinforced elements are provided for comparison. The investigations highlight fundamental differences of the flexural response of steel and carbon reinforced concrete elements. Moreover, due to the significantly higher strength-to-stiffness ratio of the CFRP reinforcement in comparison to steel, large deflections are expected for conventional prismatic beams leading to conservative designs with reduced flexural strength if deflection criteria of the serviceability limit state are to be fulfilled. Therefore, innovative designs for flexural elements reinforced with carbon are necessary if the full capacity of carbon concrete is to be utilized. Although the numerical studies in this paper are conducted using CFRP material properties, most of the obtained conclusions apply to any high-performance FRP reinforcement with linear material behavior and brittle failure. This research is a contribution in the framework of the collaborative research center CRC/TRR280 in Germany.

Keywords: *FRP, non-metallic reinforcement, CFRP reinforcement, textile reinforced concrete, carbon reinforced beams, flexural capacity, serviceability limit state, load-deflection relation, CRC/TRR280.*

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, major research efforts have been invested in developing improved composite materials to overcome the disadvantages of the conventional steel reinforced concrete and to enhance its efficiency and sustainability for construction industry. This development led to a wide range of modern concrete mixes as well as reinforcement types with advantageous properties. An appealing type of reinforcement with increasing popularity is carbon fiber-reinforced polymer (CFRP) which is a non-metallic reinforcement with superior strength-to-weight ratio and high corrosion resistance. Combining CFRP reinforcement with high-strength concrete enables the construction of thinner, efficient and high-strength structural elements. To utilize the superior material performance in flexural elements and to minimize material usage for more sustainable building, innovative concepts and designs are required to substitute or enhance the conventional prismatic elements, such as beams with rectangular cross sections, in the future. However, a fundamental understanding of the flexural behavior of these CFRP

reinforced prismatic elements and how it differs from their well-established steel reinforced counterparts is essential for further improvements of design concepts. In addition, such investigation is of a great relevance for the increasing number of research and practical applications utilizing CFRP in place of steel reinforcement [1–5] and it supports the ongoing efforts adapting current norms and guidelines for steel reinforced concrete to the new composite material with non-metallic reinforcement.

In this paper, a previously developed model for the calculation of moment-curvature relation and load-deflection behavior of flexural elements [6] is used to perform detailed numerical studies on the flexural capacity and response of CFRP reinforced beams with comparisons to their steel reinforced counterparts. The model supports arbitrary cross-section shapes, non-linear material laws and a flexible configuration of the cross-section using reinforcement layers with different materials and positioning. In addition to the parametric studies on the flexural strength, a discussion about the limitation of the deformation capacity for CFRP beams based on numerical calculations in accordance to Eurocode 2 [7] is presented.

2. MODEL ASSUMPTIONS

For the following studies, a model based on cross-section equilibrium with numerical evaluation and integration of the resulting non-linear stresses along the height of the cross-section is utilized. A range of targeted curvature values can be provided, and the corresponding moment values are evaluated assuming a linear strain distribution along the height of the cross-section which eventually lead to the full moment-curvature ($M-\kappa$) relation. The model has been described in more details in a previous publication [6] and is validated against experimental data of bending tests conducted on steel reinforced and CFRP reinforced elements.

The used material laws for the carbon and the steel reinforcement as well as for the concrete are illustrated in Figure 1. An elastic linear material law has been assumed for CFRP reinforcement up to ultimate tensile strength f_{fu} with E_f as the corresponding E-modulus. For steel, the typical multi-linear material law has been used with f_{sy} as the tensile yield strength, E_s the E-modulus and ε_{su} the rupture strain. The non-linear stress-strain relation of concrete according to the fib Model Code [8] has been used for concrete on compression with f_{cm} as the compressive strength and E_{cm} as the E-modulus of concrete. For concrete under tension, linear elastic behavior up to the tensile strength f_{ctm} has been assumed.

Figure 1. Constitutive material laws used in the numerical studies

3. FLEXURAL RESPONSE

To investigate the flexural behavior of carbon reinforced elements and to understand how it differs from the response of elements with steel reinforcement, studies with different configurations for the cross-section and varied material properties are conducted. The results are introduced in terms of the relation

between reinforcement ratio ρ and several other quantities such as ultimate moment capacity of the cross-section M_u , bending slenderness ratio L/d (beam length/effective cross-section height) and utilization ratios of the reinforcement ψ_r and of the concrete ψ_c at the ultimate moment which will be discussed in detail in the following.

3.1. Studies on a reference configuration

3.1.1. Geometry and material properties

Rectangular cross sections with identical dimensions and concrete cover are selected for both reference steel and CFRP reinforced variants, see Figure 2. The areas of the CFRP and steel reinforcement are denoted by A_f and A_s , respectively. These areas will be varied in the study by changing reinforcement ratio $\rho = A_r/b \cdot d$, where b is the width of the cross-section, d is the effective cross-section height and A_r is reinforcement area (A_s and A_f for steel and CFRP reinforcement, respectively). Figure 2 (b) shows the reference system represented by a simply supported beam with distributed load q and total applied load $F = q \cdot L$.

Figure 2. Reference configuration: (a) material properties and cross-section geometry; (b) structural system used for bending slenderness (L/d) diagrams

3.1.2. Flexural strength and material utilization

Using the reference cross sections shown in Figure 2, numerical studies have been conducted to evaluate the ultimate flexural strength M_u for reinforcement ratio values ρ between 0.2% and 2.5%. The obtained curves are illustrated in Figure 3 (a, b) for the cross sections reinforced with steel and carbon reinforcement, respectively. The balanced reinforcement ratio ρ_{fb} for FRP reinforced cross sections is defined as the reinforcement ratio at which FRP rupture and concrete compression failure occur simultaneously and it has a special significance for the calculation of the flexural capacity. According to ACI 440.1R-15 [9], this ratio can be calculated using the following equation

$$\rho_{fb} = 0.85 \cdot \beta_1 \cdot \frac{f_{cm}}{f_{fu}} \cdot \frac{E_f \cdot \epsilon_{cu}}{E_f \cdot \epsilon_{cu} + f_{fu}} \quad (1)$$

where f_{cm} is cylindrical compressive strength of concrete, β_1 a factor that depends on concrete strength ($\beta_1 = 0.85 - \frac{0.05(f_{cm}-28)}{7} \leq 0.65$ for $f_{cm} > 28$ MPa), f_{fu} ultimate tensile strength of FRP reinforcement, E_f elasticity modulus of the reinforcement and ϵ_{cu} is the ultimate strain in concrete.

Based on ρ_{fb} value, the flexural strength of FRP reinforced elements can be calculated using two equations presented in ACI 440.1R-15 [9]. A simplified equation that depends linearly on the reinforcement area A_f is used for reinforcement ratios below ρ_{fb} corresponding to a FRP rupture failure, and a non-linear equation is used for ratios larger than ρ_{fb} for cases in which the concrete fails under compression. The relation between the flexural strength and reinforcement ratio obtained using the ACI

code is plotted in blue in Figure 3 (b). The corresponding balanced reinforcement ratio was $f_{fb} = 0.21\%$ which is indicated using a dotted blue line in the same figure. The flexural strength curve obtained from the ACI code produces a conservative estimation in comparison with the curve from the simulation based on numerical evaluation of the exact non-linear stress distribution along the cross-section.

The steel reinforced cross-section has a linear $M_u - \rho$ relation along the whole ρ range. For the CFRP reinforced section, the $M_u - \rho$ curves obtained from ACI based calculation and from the simulation are plotted in Figure 3 (b) showing almost an identical behavior except a slight difference at the beginning, which is due to the consideration of the concrete tensile strength in the simulation. The simulation yields a flexural strength value of 168 kNm at $\rho = 2.5\%$ for steel, while delivering the value of 205 kNm for the identical cross-section with carbon reinforcement. This means, despite the remarkably higher strength of the carbon reinforcement, the difference in flexural strength is not significant in this point because of the concrete compression failure and the low utilization ratio of the carbon reinforcement.

The utilization of the reinforcement, denoted by ψ_r , is calculated as $\sigma_{r,u}/f_{sy}$ or $\sigma_{r,u}/f_{fu}$ for steel reinforcement and carbon reinforcement, respectively, where $\sigma_{r,u}$ is the reinforcement stress in the cross-section at the ultimate flexural strength M_u . Also, the utilization of concrete is defined as $\psi_c = \sigma_{c,u}/f_{cm}$ in analogy to ψ_r , where $\sigma_{c,u}$ is compression stress in concrete at the M_u . The relation between both utilization ratios and reinforcement ratio ρ is illustrated in Figure 3 (c, d) for steel and carbon reinforced cross-sections, respectively. The ratio ρ_{fb} can be identified as a kink in the $M_u - \rho$ curve in Figure 3 (a) that indicates the transition from the linear branch controlled by CFRP tensile failure to the non-linear branch controlled by concrete failure. It also represents the transition from a state where CFRP reinforcement is fully utilized to a phase with a rapid non-linear decrease in CFRP utilization ratio as Figure 3 (d) shows. The simulation yielded a balanced reinforcement value $\rho_{fb} = 0.28\%$ which is indicated using a vertical dotted line that separates the two failure zones shaded with red and gray color for $\rho < \rho_{fb}$ and $\rho > \rho_{fb}$, respectively. In contrary to CFRP reinforcement, we see that steel will be fully utilized through the whole studied ρ range due to its yielding capacity and low strength in comparison to CFRP reinforcement.

To provide a relative comparison between the performance of the steel versus CFRP reinforcement, we introduce the ratio $\alpha_{c/s} = M_{u,carbon}/M_{u,steel}$ between the ultimate flexural strength of the carbon reinforced cross-section and the corresponding value of the steel reinforced variant. The ratio $\alpha_{c/s}$ is plotted in Figure 3 (g) over the whole range of the reinforcement ratio ρ , showing a maximum value of 4.8 at $\rho = 0.2\%$.

3.1.3. Maximum load capacity for simply supported beam

The design space for conventional prismatic beams with rectangular cross sections can be well covered using a practical range of reinforcement ratio $\rho = A_r/b \cdot d$ with bending slenderness ratio L/d . Figure 3 (e, f) show contour lines of the maximum load capacity $F_u = q \cdot L$ that corresponds to a grid of ρ and L/d values for steel and carbon reinforced sections, respectively. These contour lines illustrate how this maximum load capacity is distributed through the design space and demonstrate the difference between flexural responses of elements reinforced with CFRP and steel. In contrast to steel which shows a relatively regular distribution with rather linear contour lines, the contour lines of the CFRP reinforced element cumulate in the tensile failure zone ($\rho < \rho_{fb}$) and develop non-linearly from a vertical to a horizontal orientation towards smaller slenderness ratios L/d in the compression failure zone ($\rho > \rho_{fb}$). Therefore, the lower the slenderness ratio, the less the significance of the reinforcement ratio. For example, in contrast to steel reinforced beams, a beam with CFRP reinforcement and a ratio $L/d = 5$ brings about only a negligible improvement in the ultimate load capacity F_u when increasing reinforcement ratio ρ beyond 1% because the ultimate load remains nearly constant at the level of $F_u \cong 1000$ kN. Figure 3 (h) exemplifies load-deflection curves for steel and CFRP reinforced elements in a selected point ($\rho = 2\%, L/d = 10$). The CFRP variant shows no significant improvement in the ultimate load in comparison with the steel reinforced element here due to the low CFRP utilization ratio as discussed earlier.

Figure 3. Flexural behavior of reference configuration: (a, b) relation between flexural strength and reinforcement ratio; (c, d) reinforcement ratio relation to material utilization factors; (e, f) contour lines of ultimate load capacity; (g) the ratio $\alpha_{c/s}$ between flexural strength of CFRP and steel plotted against ρ ; (h) load-deflection curves of a selected point with ($L/d = 10$ and $\rho = 2\%$)

3.2. Parametric studies

In the following, the effect of multiple parameters on the flexural behavior is studied. In each case, only the corresponding parameter is varied, while all other material and geometric properties remain the same as the reference configuration presented in the previous section.

3.2.1. Effect of concrete grade

The effect of three different concrete grades denoted as C40, C70 and C100 according to the classification of fib Model Code [8] was analysed using the model. The obtained results are depicted in Figure 4 with the legend provided in Figure 4 (f). As apparent from Figure 4 (a, b), only a minor increase in flexural strength is obtained for higher concrete grades in the case of steel reinforcement in comparison to carbon reinforcement. The increase in concrete strength causes a shift in carbon reinforcement utilization (dashed lines) yielding higher flexural strength values in concrete compression failure zone, see Figure 4 (b, d). As a consequence, this also leads to a higher $\alpha_{c/s}$ factor for higher concrete grades, see Figure 4 (e). However, in case of steel, the concrete strength is only fully activated for higher ρ values as concrete utilization ψ_c curves show in Figure 4 (c).

Figure 4. The effect of different concrete grades on the flexural behavior

3.2.2. Effect of hybrid reinforcement

Hybrid reinforcement, i.e., combined steel and CFRP reinforcement in the same cross-section, can increase the cross-sectional bending performance in the form of a semi-ductile behavior and high

ultimate load. In addition to the reference steel and CFRP reinforced cross sections, two variants with hybrid reinforcement were investigated. Reinforcement ratios ρ_f and ρ_s for CFRP and steel, respectively were varied for the two sections and were taken as a percentage from the total reinforcement ratio ρ as shown in Figure 5 (a). The study shows a non-proportional effect of the carbon reinforcement fraction on the overall cross-sectional capacity. We demonstrate that by replacing 20% of steel with carbon reinforcement (*hybrid 2* cross-section), up to 75% improvement in flexural strength can be achieved as Figure 5 (b) illustrates and as the value $\alpha_{h/s, hybrid, max} = 1.75$ in Figure 5 (c) indicates. The balanced reinforcement ratio for *hybrid 2* cross-section is large in comparison with the pure CFRP and *hybrid 1* (50% CFRP reinforcement) sections providing a better CFRP utilization as Figure 5 (d) demonstrates. The ratio of the additional gain in the flexural strength obtained for hybrid cross sections to the section with pure CFRP reinforcement calculated as $\alpha_{h/s}/\alpha_{c/s}$, where $\alpha_{h/s} = M_{u, hybrid}/M_{u, steel}$, yields maximum values exactly at the balanced reinforcement ratio of the corresponding cross-section. The values are $2.8/3.45 = 81\%$ and $1.73/2.5 = 70\%$ for *hybrid 1* (50% CFRP) and *hybrid 2* (20% CFRP) cross sections, respectively. That means, substitution of only 20% of the steel reinforcement with CFRP could produce up to 70% of the performance of the pure CFRP section and up to 81% by using a section with 50% CFRP.

Figure 5. Flexural behavior of cross sections with hybrid reinforcement

3.2.3. Effect of cross-section shape

In addition to the rectangular cross-section used in the reference configuration, T-section and I-section with large upper flange have been studied using both steel and CFRP reinforcement. All three cross-sections have the same effective cross-section height d and cross-section area A_c as illustrated in Figure 6 (g). The two chosen non-rectangular cross sections produced almost identical results except a small shift in concrete utilization curve for $\rho < 0.5\%$ for the case of steel reinforcement, see Figure 6 (c). A shift in balanced reinforcement ratio ρ_{fb} for carbon reinforced variant resulted in an increased utilization of the carbon reinforcement (Figure 6 (d)) and consequently to a significant improvement in flexural strength up to $(343-205)/205 = 67\%$ at $\rho = 2.5\%$ compared to a rectangular cross section, see Figure 6 (b). On the other hand, an increase of only $(194-178)/178 = 9\%$ has been obtained for the steel reinforced sections, see Figure 6 (a). Therefore, the usage of flanged cross sections such as T-sections or I-sections provides much larger advantage for CFRP reinforced sections in comparison with the equivalent sections with steel reinforcement. This can also be observed in Figure 6 (e) where the additional gain in

flexural strength caused by the usage of flanged cross sections in comparison to rectangular sections represented by $\alpha_{c/s}$ (flanged section) - $\alpha_{c/s}$ (rect. section) is shaded in grey color and ranging from a maximum value of 1.4 (at $\rho = 0.5\%$) to value of 0.5 (at $\rho = 2.5\%$).

Figure 6. Flexural behavior of non-rectangular cross sections with same height and cross-sectional area

4. LIMIT DEFLECTION IN SLS

A simplified approach for avoiding excessive deflections in SLS is provided in Eurocode 2 [7] and fib Model Code [8] which prescribe limits to the slenderness ratio L/d (span to effective depth). Exceeding these limits yields inadmissible deflections beyond $w_{limit} = L/250$ for the corresponding serviceability load F_{SLS} . The limit values of L/d ratio for CFRP reinforced elements were calculated using the same assumptions of the Eurocode 2 including the ratio of serviceability load (quasi-permanent load) F_{SLS} to

the total design load F_{ult} , see Figure 7 (d). The obtained curve for concrete grade C40 is plotted in Figure 7 (a) together with the corresponding curve for steel reinforced element according to Eurocode 2. Additional L/d curve for concrete grade C30 and different FRP reinforcement properties derived by El Ghadioui 2020 [10] is also plotted as dashed black line which shows a similar trend to the dashed green curve obtained from current simulation. The curves calculated for FRP reinforcement demonstrate much stricter limits in comparison to their steel counterpart especially at the balanced reinforcement value ρ_{fb} which corresponds to the lowest point in L/d curves. This is due to the high strength-to-stiffness ratio of the FRP reinforcement (especially CFRP) in comparison with steel reinforcement which yields large deflection values when utilizing the full capacity of the cross-section. This fact becomes clear when observing load-deflection curves obtained from the simulation for two different points located exactly on the limiting L/d curves for steel and CFRP reinforcement as shown in Figure 7 (b, c). At the orange point which matches the L/d limit of steel at $\rho = 0.5\%$, w_{limit} has a value equal to $w_{SLS,steel}$ which is the deflection corresponding to the service load for steel reinforced element. Considering a CFRP reinforced beam at the same point ($\rho = 0.5\%$, $L/d = 25$), much larger deflections compared to steel reinforced beam are achieved (see solid curve in Figure 7 (b)). As a result, the service load $F_{SLS,CFRP}$ yields a deflection $w_{SLS,CFRP}$ larger than the prescribed limit w_{limit} . It is certainly possible to use this CFRP reinforced beam with $L/d = 25$. However, only for a reduced value of the ultimate load capacity by approximately 50%. Obviously, this configuration is not economical. Figure 7 (c) shows load-deflection curves corresponding to the point ($\rho = 0.5\%$, $L/d = 7$). The load-deflection curve of the CFRP variant shows an admissible deflection state with full utilization of ultimate load capacity.

Figure 7. Limiting deflections in SLS: (a) Limiting L/d curves for ensuring admissible deflections; (b, c) load-deflections curves on two points corresponding to the L/d limit of steel and CFRP reinforced elements; (d) system and cross-section assumed in provided SLS study

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, numerical studies using variable cross-sections and material properties have been conducted to investigate the behavior of CFRP reinforced flexural elements with comparisons to their steel reinforced counterparts. Flexural strength of steel and CFRP reinforced cross sections obtained from the used model and from calculations based on ACI code shows a good agreement, with slightly

lower strength prediction delivered by the ACI code. The studied CFRP reinforced section provides up to almost five times higher flexural strength in the tensile failure zone. However, for reinforcement ratio values larger than the balanced reinforcement ratio, concrete compression failure dominates and a rapid non-linear decrease in the utilization of the CFRP reinforcement reduces this factor from 5 to 1.2 at reinforcement ratio $\rho=2.5\%$. The studies also show that in concrete crushing failure zone, the lower the slenderness L/d is, the less the significance of reinforcement ratio in terms of the ultimate load capacity of a simply supported beam under distributed load.

Parametric studies also indicated a remarkably larger increase in the flexural capacity of CFRP reinforced sections in comparison to their steel reinforced counterparts when using higher concrete grades or flanged cross sections (T and I sections) with the same height and cross-section area as the reference rectangular sections. Additionally, the study on hybrid cross sections with mixed steel and CFRP reinforcement demonstrates that using hybrid sections with as low as 20% CFRP share provides up to 70% of the performance of the pure CFRP reinforced one.

It was also illustrated that due to the significantly higher strength-to-stiffness ratio of carbon reinforcement in comparison to steel, large deflections are expected especially for small reinforcement ratios. If deflection limits of SLS are to be enforced, significant percentage of the flexural strength capacity must remain unused in the cross-sectional design. Therefore, further studies are needed to develop enhanced CFRP reinforced flexural elements with innovative non-rectangular or possibly non-prismatic configurations that mitigate excessive deflections with providing high material utilization.

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